

"The Application of Translation Aids in the Translation Process of Informative Texts".

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Abstract: *The article views the opportunities of information and communication technologies as a method for soon-to-be interpreters and translators professional motivation formation.*

Keywords: *information and communication technologies, professional motivation.*

In today's world, the volume of text documents created in the languages of the peoples of the world, which, in turn, led to an increase in demand for translation services, to the expansion of the translation industry as a whole. For optimization translation process, translators need to actively use modern information technology, since the use of the latest methods allows to achieve high-quality and prompt translation of large amounts of information. Internet resources translators use both for professional communication and for searching for information in specialized areas, linguistic information. Modern translators actively turn to electronic dictionaries (ABBYY Lingvo, Multitran, Multilex) and special software that helps to automate and optimize the translation process. It should be borne in mind that specialized translation programs include automated translation systems (translation memory class software) and machine translation (or automatic translation), and they need to be separated. If automated translation (Computer Assisted Translation (CAT) is software used by a human translator in translation process to increase productivity, then machine translation (MT) is a computer technology that when translation from one language to another is performed computer program without human intervention. Automatic translation programs allow the use of previously translated texts. During the translation process, the program saves in translation memories (in the database) original and translated segments of text that are named translation units. Each time the translator starts translating a new segment of text, that segment is matched against the translation units contained in the database. If the memory translation contains the same or similar segment. The program analyzes the database and finds it and automatically substitutes it in the translation text instead of the original fragment. If the option proposed by the program is an inexact match, then the translator can change it, then is to edit and add it

to the translation memory, due to which the information capacity of the translation memory is constantly increasing.

At the same time, it should be borne in mind that, although the use of an automated translation program reduces the time of translation and increases its quality, the main translation work (text analysis, selection of one or another translation strategy) is performed by a person. A translation automation system is, first of all, a tool facilitating the work of the translator. Translation Automation Tools (CAT-Tools) provide higher translation quality due to the uniformity of terminology and style, allow you to save original formatting, reduce time costs, allow you to create and effectively use a term base, create a translation memory based on already translated texts and their originals, manage translation projects and supervise the work carried out by the translation team. The original results were obtained during scientific study on the use of computer-aided translation programs by translators in their professional activities, by Elina Lagudaki from Imperial College London. She conducted an online survey of more than 800 professional translators from 54 countries. And, as the survey showed, 82.5% translators used in their professional activities programs of automated translation. At the same time, it was noted that the most popular among translators are such software solutions as SDL Trados, Wordfast, Déjà Vu, STAR Transit, OmegaT [1].

As mentioned above, unlike automated translation, automatic, or machine translation, carries out the process of translation without human intervention, while it is quite natural. Mandatory editing of the translated text is required. The first attempts to create machine translation programs were made in the 40s. the last century. J.K. Cutford proposes special rules, which are "extrapolation of the probabilistic values of textual translated equivalences" as for a human translator, as well as for machine translation. "For a human translator, rules are established that allow refer to contextual meanin" [2, With. 61]. For the purposes of machine translation, translation rules may take the form of operational commands for textual search of elements marked in the machine dictionary with special diacritics, with order to print in each case a specific conditional equivalent. J.K. Cutford calls such operational commands "translation algorithms". If they are performed exactly, then, according to him opinion, it is possible to guarantee a high degree the probability of "correctness" of the translation. Algorithms translation, according to J. K. Cutford, should be based on equivalences with probabilities, approaching 1 [2, p. 62]. There is a tendency to consider machine translation to be initial stages, when the problem of developing algorithms is being

solved, which "to a large extent probabilities will produce moderately intelligible translations, like "recoding". However, J.K. Cutford is convinced that for a deeper understanding of translation view of it as a process "transcoding" is unsuitable [2, p. 82].

J.K. Cutford rightly refers to the problems of machine translation the issues of "linguistic untranslatability" and the so-called "culturological untranslatability" of individual units translation. The researcher is convinced that if one finds the ability to identify them in the text of the translation, then they "could be introduced into computer programs and used in machine translation" [2, p. 196].

Professional translators frowned upon the emergence of the first machine translation programs. On the one hand, translators did not believe in the very possibility of an adequate translation of textual materials using machines, with on the other hand, they expressed fear that machine translation programs would force them out of this professional environment. We suppose, however, that there is no reason to believe that the machine translation can compete with a human translator. Although the developers of modern software in the field of machine translators are making considerable efforts so that the computer can replace a person in the future in the translation process, those translation programs that exist at the moment, while still very imperfect. Machine translation tools are effective when it is necessary to translate technical texts, user manuals, instructions, but are of little use for the translation of fiction, advertising texts, articles.

LITERATURE:

1. Lagoudaki E. Translation Memories Survey, 2006. URL: <http://www3.imperial.ac.uk/portal/pls/portallive/docs/1/7307707.PDF>.
2. J. K. Cutford. Linguistic Translation Theory: About one aspect of applied linguistics. Per. from English. Ed. 2nd. M.: Knizhny dom LIBROKOM, 2009. 208.
3. Lagoudaki E. The Value of Machine Translation for the Professional Translator. AMTA-2008. MT at work: Proceedings of the Eighth Conference of the Association for Machine Translation in the Americas, Waikiki, Hawaii, October 21–25, 262–269 URL: <http://www.translationjournal.net>.
4. Zetsche J. Machine Translation Revisited. Translation Journal. Volume 11, No. 1, January 2007 URL: <http://www.translationjournal.net>.
5. Sysoykina M. "Ce-BIT: the world is becoming flat". URL: <http://osp.ru/PCWorld/2008/04/5174907>.

